
THE SPIRITUAL INFLUENCE OF ORIENTAL VALUES IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUTH OF OUR SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

In the years of independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the impact of oriental values on the formation of the legal consciousness and culture of young people in our society is discussed. Therefore, this article evaluates the unique aspects of the Uzbek national mentality and its role in the formation of youth behavior and life aspirations.

Keywords: National values, tradition, national spirituality, consciousness, patriotism, spiritual heritage, purity, independence, internationalism, generosity.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В годы независимости в Республике Узбекистан обсуждается влияние восточных ценностей на формирование правосознания и культуры молодежи нашего общества. Поэтому в данной статье оцениваются уникальные стороны узбекского национального менталитета и его роль в формировании поведения молодежи и жизненных устремлений.

Ключевые слова: Национальные ценности, традиции, национальная духовность, сознание, патриотизм, духовное наследие, чистота, независимость, интернационализм, великодушие.

INTRODUCTION

An important factor that forms spirituality in young people is the education system. It is necessary to look at knowledge, our values, and education as the main condition for human maturity and development of the nation. For this reason, it is established in our general dictionary that the issue of education and upbringing of young people is under the control of the state.

From the first days of our country's independence, attention has been paid to youth education, and raising a physically healthy and intellectually mature generation has been set as a priority. He rose to the level of state policy. State programs named

after the year "Mother and Child", "Youth", "Perfect Generation", "Family", "Prosperous Life" and their implementation,

It is an expression of the good intentions of our people for a bright future. First of all, the programs defined the tasks of forming a well-rounded generation that is physically and mentally healthy, independent-thinking, possessing a scientific and modern outlook, deep knowledge, and a sense of patriotism and nationalism.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

A national, intellectual and cultural space is being created in our country. Since ancient times, many ethnic groups and peoples have played a small part in the creation of our culture. Because there is never, anywhere, a culture belonging to only one nation. As our head of state noted: "Any civilization is a product of the activities and effective influence of many peoples, nations, peoples. In a word, settlers and invaders will come and go, but the nation will remain forever, its culture will live forever."

The civilization and culture of the East is always preparing the people for great changes spiritually and spiritually.

The highest value is the person himself, but during the Soviet era, the person was not appreciated. Yusuf Khos Khajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Ahmad Yassavi, Amir Temur, the great sons of our nation, were not appreciated. Intelligent scholars like Alisher Navoi, Babur, Ulug'bek, Mashrab, Nodirabegim were humiliated as representatives of the feudal era, and it was forbidden to study their rich unique heritage.

The whole world sees the inexhaustible, multifaceted, rich spiritual and moral glory of the people of Uzbekistan, all citizens. The culture, language, history, customs and traditions of our people, the rich art of architecture arouse great interest in the peoples of the world.

Bringing our national culture closer to regional and universal human values, strengthening and further developing our cultural ties with the peoples of the world is an important direction of our government's policy. The actions taken in this regard are notable for their comprehensiveness and versatility.

The long-standing traditions, culture, traditions, national holidays, rich ancient heritage of our people have a special place and importance in the development of the elements of social activity in young people through our national values. On the basis of the formation and strengthening of national pride, national pride among young people, special importance has been given to increasing their social activities. Mental

intelligence, mental and spiritual maturity, honesty, kindness, kindness - all these are the main qualities of enlightened and spiritual people. Forming these qualities in our youth is an important task today. In the current globalization process, a person who is disciplined, responsible, patient, pious, conscientious, faithful, tolerant, humane, socially active and the owner of such noble qualities only young people are able to create all the comforts necessary for living. The process of democratic development of social development is directly related to the self-awareness of the individual, to what extent he respects his dignity, the ability to serve the society and his actions. All this is related to the social activity of a person.

CONCLUSION

Social activation of today's youth means their conscious and independent participation in social processes, and when necessary, they strive to help change social relations without external pressure. Responsibility is one of the important indicators that determine the maturity of a person in the process of socialization is counted. Another direction of socialization related to the sense of responsibility is the individual are goals and ideals that are formed. They always provide a person with the ability to see the future, imagine the future, and be ready to implement long-term plans. A person without goals and plans is a pessimist without spirituality. It is characterized by its awareness and dependence on the real capabilities of a person. In a certain sense, it plays an ideal role in their formation and settling in the mind. The theoretical views collected in the world science on the development of the human personality and the experience of Uzbekistan show that the social activity of the human personality is formed, first of all, in the community, in certain types of activities. Since the student period is a period of social activity and wide opportunities for the manifestation of various moral norms, the educational process, which is considered a priority activity among young people, is an important factor.

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